

BDV Data Science Badges – A Case Study of the Use of the EDISON EDSF

By Ernestina Menasalvas, Ana M. Moreno, and Nik Swoboda
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

- Portions of this document were taken from *D4.6: A Framework for the Recognition of Data Science Skills in Europe* and *D4.2: Skills, Education, and Centers of Excellence Period I Report* which were produced as part of the Big Data Value Ecosystem project.
- This work was partially funded by the project ID: 732630 funded under: H2020-EU.2.1.1. - INDUSTRIAL LEADERSHIP - Leadership in enabling and industrial technologies - Information and Communication Technologies.

Contents

1	INTRODUCTION	3
1.1	HOW CAN WE STANDARDIZE CREDENTIALS THROUGHOUT EUROPE?	3
1.2	HOW CAN DATA SCIENCE CREDENTIALS BE: DIGITAL, VERIFIABLE, GRANULAR, AND QUICKLY EVOLVING?	4
1.3	OVERVIEW	4
2	THE STRATEGIC FRAMEWORK FOR EDUCATION AND TRAINING 20205	
2.1	NEW SKILLS AGENDA FOR EUROPE	6
2.2	NEW EUROPASS FRAMEWORK	7
2.3	EUROPEAN QUALIFICATIONS FRAMEWORK FOR LIFELONG LEARNING	8
2.4	EUROPEAN SKILLS, COMPETENCES, QUALIFICATIONS AND OCCUPATIONS	11
2.5	HIGHLIGHTS AND COMMON THREADS IN THESE INITIATIVES	12
3	A SURVEY OF RECOGNITIONS	13
3.1	ACCREDITATIONS	13
3.2	UNIVERSITY/ACADEMIC DEGREES	13
3.3	CERTIFICATES	14
3.4	LABELS	15
3.5	BADGES	15
3.6	A COMPARISON OF RECOGNITIONS	16
3.6.1	Properties specific to data science	16
3.6.2	The comparison	16
3.7	DISCUSSION	18
4	RECOMMENDATIONS REGARDING DATA SCIENCE SKILLS RECOGNITION	19
4.1	THE LOGISTICS OF THE BDV DATA SCIENCE BADGE PROGRAM	22
5	BDV DATA SCIENCE BADGES TYPES AND REQUIREMENTS	24
5.1	REFINING AND EVALUATING THIS INITIAL PROPOSAL	25
6	CONCLUSIONS	28

1 Introduction

With the development of new technology and the digital transformation of our economy, the labor market has also evolved. Nowadays, applicants for a job are no longer asked to submit a traditional paper resume, this information is presented digitally; recruiters and headhunters search the Internet (on an international level) for candidates who have the required skills for their needs; and some assessment of candidates can be done on-line. Moreover, the demands for labor are constantly evolving and the required skills and qualifications change rapidly over time. Adequately adapting to these changes is essential for the success of: employers, learning institutions, and governmental agencies related to education.

In this chapter, we will first discuss mechanisms for recognizing skills in the EU with a focus on the internationalization, digitalization, and flexibility of those credentials. Then we will consider their application to data science with the goal of proposing a new framework for the recognition skills in data science. We begin with a brief review of the main challenges we hope to address.

1.1 How can we standardize credentials throughout Europe?

Although political institutions in the EU have strived to coordinate and standardize diplomas and other forms of credentialing in higher education, the variety of educational systems in the EU and the lack of an adequate system to recognize learning and skills have contributed to great differences in the economic and social outcomes of the member states. The many different educational and training systems in Europe make it difficult for employers to evaluate the capabilities of potential employees.

Currently, there is no automatic system for the EU-wide recognition of academic diplomas¹; students can only request a "statement of comparability" for their university degree. This statement of comparability details how the student's diploma compares to the diplomas of another EU country.² Something similar happens with the recognition of professional qualifications: the mobility of Europeans between member states of the EU often requires the full recognition of their professional qualifications (training and professional experience). This is accomplished through an established procedure in each European country.³ Directives 2005/36/EC and 2013/55/UE on the recognition of professional qualifications, establish guidelines that

¹ It should be noted that at the time of writing there are efforts underway to establish by 2025 the "automatic mutual recognition of higher education and upper secondary education and training qualifications" [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018H1210\(01\)&from=EN](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018H1210(01)&from=EN), in the EU but it appears that a great deal of work is still needed to accomplish this goal.

² http://europa.eu/youreurope/citizens/education/university/recognition/index_en.htm (Consulted December 2019)

³ http://europa.eu/youreurope/citizens/work/professional-qualifications/recognition-of-professional-qualifications/index_en.htm (Consulted December 2019)

allow professionals to work in another EU country, different from the one where they obtained their professional qualification, on the basis of a declaration.

These directives provide three systems of recognition:

- automatic recognition – for professions with harmonized minimum training conditions, i.e., nurses, midwives, doctors, dentists, pharmacists, architects and veterinary surgeons;
- general system – for other regulated professions such as teachers, translators and real estate agents;
- recognition on the basis of professional experience - for certain professional activities such as carpenters, upholsterers, beauticians etc.;

Additionally, since January 18, 2016 the European professional card (EPC) has been available for five professions (general care nurses, physiotherapists, pharmacists, real estate agents and mountain guides). It is an electronic certificate which can be applied for online.

Unfortunately, these existing mechanisms do not easily accommodate many professions including that of data science.

1.2 How can data science credentials be: digital, verifiable, granular, and quickly evolving?

Traditionally skills and credentials were conveyed via a resume on paper and other paper-based credentials. Nowadays, this information can be shared via the Internet in web pages, social media, and in many other forms. The digitalization of credentials not only allows easier access but also offers new possibilities like:

- the online verification of the validity of the credentials,
- greater granularity in the definition of the credentials,
- the expiration of credentials requiring their periodic renewal which could take into account changes in the demands for skills, and
- access to the evidence used in the awarding of credentials.

Future schemes for the recognition of skills need to adapt to and accommodate these new demands.

1.3 Overview

This chapter begins with a summary of current trends regarding education and skills in Europe. From these trends, we extract a series of desirable properties for a data science skills recognition scheme. Then, a survey of different mechanisms for the recognition of skills is presented. Next, a comparison and critical analysis of these recognitions is provided while taking into account the previously identified desirable properties. Lastly, a recommendation for a data science skills recognition process is proposed.

2 The Strategic Framework for Education and Training 2020

Even though the educational systems of each country in the EU are managed separately at the national level, a common EU policy exists to support those systems and to help address common challenges faced by the EU. The Strategic Framework for Education & Training 2020 (ET-2020) contains the current policies of the EC for cooperation on education and training. These policies were initially adopted in 2009⁴ and contain four common objectives that should be met by 2020 in the EU:

- Making lifelong learning and mobility a reality.
- Improving the quality and efficiency of education and training.
- Promoting equity, social cohesion, and active citizenship.
- Enhancing creativity and innovation, including entrepreneurship, at all levels of education and training.

In reviewing the progress of the ET-2020, the *2015 Joint Report of the Council and the Commission on the implementation of the strategic framework for European cooperation in education and training*⁵ (2015-JR-SFECT) included a new set of “priority areas for European cooperation in education and training”:

1. Relevant and high-quality skills and competences for employability, innovation, active citizenship
2. Inclusive education, equality, non-discrimination, civic competences
3. Open and innovative education and training, including by fully embracing the digital era
4. Strong support for educators
5. Transparency and recognition of skills and qualifications
6. Sustainable investment, performance and efficiency of education and training systems

As the emphasis on promoting the “transparency and recognition of skills and qualifications” is particularly relevant to the task of recognizing data science skills we will focus further on that priority area. To explain this priority area, the report identifies these concrete needs:

- Fostering transparency, quality assurance, validation and recognition of skills and/or qualifications, including those acquired through digital, online and open learning and the validation of informal and non-formal learning

⁴ [http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52009XG0528\(01\)&from=EN](http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52009XG0528(01)&from=EN)
(Consulted December 2019)

⁵ [http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52015XG1215\(02\)&from=EN](http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52015XG1215(02)&from=EN)
(Consulted December 2019)

- Simplifying and rationalizing the transparency, documentation, validation and recognition tools that involve direct outreach to learners, workers and employers and further implementing the EQF [European Qualifications Framework for lifelong learning] and NQFs [National Qualifications Frameworks]
- Supporting the mobility of pupils, apprentices, students, teachers, members of educational staff and researchers
- Developing strategic partnerships and joint courses, in particular through increasing internationalization of higher education and vocational education and training

To help reach these goals the EU has promoted several programs:

- The **European Qualifications Framework for Lifelong Learning (EQF)** supports the process of validating qualifications by providing a common reference for qualification levels throughout Europe and the linking of member state validation systems with formal qualifications systems.
- **Validation of non-formal and informal learning** is the process of recognizing an individual's knowledge, skills and competences gained outside formal educational systems. To help to achieve this recognition, the CEDEFOP (European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training) in cooperation with the EC have defined some guidelines for validating non-formal and informal learning.⁶ They have also proposed an up-to-date European Inventory that provides an overview for each country and good practices for the design and implementation of validation initiatives.
- The **Europass portfolio** also relates to validation systems because it documents learning and enables users to display their skills, qualifications and experiences in a uniform way across Europe.
- The **European Credit Transfer and Accumulation** system for higher education⁷ and the **European Credit system for Vocational Education and Training (ECVET)**⁸ standardize the quantification of formal learning throughout Europe, making it easier to compare the time spent in educational programs.
- **Quality assurance** arrangements in higher education and vocational training to make education systems easier to understand for students and employers, by improving transparency tools.

We will now elaborate more upon the most relevant points of a number of key initiatives within this framework.

2.1 New Skills Agenda for Europe

The New Skills Agenda for Europe (NSAE) is one of the initiatives of the EU to help meet the targets of the ET-2020. On June 10, 2016, the European Commission

⁶ Cedefop (2015). European guidelines for validating non-formal and informal learning. Luxembourg: Publications Office. Cedefop reference series; No 104. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2801/008370>

⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/education/resources-and-tools/european-credit-transfer-and-accumulation-system-ects_en (Consulted January 2020)

⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/education/resources-and-tools/the-european-credit-system-for-vocational-education-and-training-ecvet_en (Consulted January 2020)

presented this agenda⁹, which sets out different guidelines to guarantee that the most adequate training, skills and career guidance is accessible to everyone in the EU.

The New Skills agenda emphasizes “the strategic importance of skills for sustaining jobs, growth and competitiveness,” and is focused on three key points:

- Improving the quality and relevance of skills formation
- Making skills and qualifications more visible and comparable
- Improving skills intelligence and information for better career choices

The most relevant concerns and recommendations mentioned in the New Skills Agenda regarding data science skills in Europe include:

- Future credentials should easily allow the comparison of students’ skills throughout the EU.
- Both the employed and the unemployed need adequate ways to present their skills and qualifications. Employers need ways to identify and recruit new employees with the skills that they need.
- Once skills qualifications are easily accessible, current and future demands for skills could be identified with data science analysis (skills intelligence).
- Current qualification systems focus on the learning outcomes of formal education programs, but do not validate non-formal and informal learning. Ongoing learning, including learning at the workplace, needs to be encouraged.
- Skills acquisition should not only be in formal education and training (literacy, numeracy, science, foreign languages) but also transversal skills (teamwork, creative analysis, problem solving, entrepreneurship, etc.).

2.2 New Europass framework

In February 2005, the Europass was launched, following the decision of the European Parliament and the Council¹⁰ to create a single framework whose goal was to make individuals skills and qualifications more comprehensible in Europe. This was done in the interest of facilitating the mobility of students and workers. The Europass consisted of a portfolio of five documents: the Europass Curriculum Vitae (CV); the Europass Language Passport; the Europass Mobility; the Europass Certificate Supplement; and the Europass Diploma Supplement.

Despite the fact that the European CV has undergone significant improvements to adapt to the changes brought by the technological revolution, the initial Europass did not address the changing educational, training and labor market conditions:¹¹

- It focused on documents and templates that are not compatible with the use of social media, mobile devices, Big Data analysis and job matching tools;

9 <http://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1223> (Consulted January 2020)

10 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32004D2241&from=EN> (Consulted January 2020)

11 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52013DC0899&from=en> (Consulted January 2020)

- It did not face the growing relevance of modern learning, that needed an easy way to record skills and qualifications acquired through non-formal or informal learning, including on-line learning;
- It did not take into account the use of tools such as ‘open badges.’¹²

On October 4, 2016 the Commission decided to revise the Europass Decision, by building a new Europass framework that contributes to the display of people’s skills and qualifications in a unified manner for all EU countries.¹³

The proposal addresses challenges regarding the way that information technology has changed the labor market and new educational possibilities:

- The publication of employment offers, job applications, candidate’s evaluation and recruiting are increasingly done online through tools that use social media, Big Data and other technologies, making it easier to find information on skills and qualifications.
- Education and training is increasingly offered on-line using digital platforms; at the same time, skills, experiences and learning achievements (formal and non-formal) are recognized in different forms, such as open badges.

With the new framework users can display their skills and qualifications in new formats, as the revised Europass uses open standards to facilitate the exchange of electronic data and defines authentication measures to ensure the validity of the digital content.

To achieve this goal, the new infrastructure includes several new tools, which allow users to give evidence of their skills and qualifications in all EU languages; these tools are:

- An online tool to create persona profiles, including both the traditional CV, with work experience and training/education and the skills recognition.
- Applications to help to evaluate the users’ skills
- Information on learning opportunities across Europe
- Assistance on how to get a user’s skills recognized
- Labor market intelligence, to learn which skills are more valuable

The new Europass is connected to other EU tools and services related to work, education and training systems, to encourage the exchange of information and to help users in their education and career path decisions.

2.3 European Qualifications Framework for lifelong learning

In April 2008, the European Parliament and Council resolved to establish the European Qualifications Framework for Lifelong Learning.¹⁴ The process was voluntary, and countries were invited to implement the framework in two stages: the first, that was

¹² An open badge is a digital token used as form of digital recognition of learning which can be displayed digitally.

¹³ <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regdoc/rep/1/2016/EN/1-2016-625-EN-F1-1.PDF> (Consulted January 2020)

¹⁴ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2008:111:0001:0007:EN:PDF> (Consulted January 2020)

to be completed by 2010, relating national qualification levels to the EQF; and the second, by 2012, ensuring that all new qualifications issued in Europe include references to the appropriate EQF level.

The aim of this framework is to provide a way to compare and interpret the levels of different qualification in the EU and thereby make those qualifications more transparent. This also facilitates mobility, having positive effects for learners and workers, who can have their level of competence recognized using a standard description all across Europe. This proposal is also beneficial for recruiters and education providers, who will be able to understand the applicants' qualifications. The adoption of a common reference framework eases the comparison and recognition of traditional qualifications issued by national authorities and those awarded by third parties (e.g., multinational companies). This allows the comparison of formal and non-formal education by increasing the transparency of qualifications awarded outside the formal education system.

The EQF can be applied to any kind of education, training or qualification including required basic education to advanced academic and professional and training. It consists of eight qualification levels, given in terms of learning outcomes¹⁵: knowledge, skills and competences. These levels take into consideration theoretical knowledge, practical skills, technical skills, and social competences. The following table gives the descriptions of the eight levels included in the EQF:¹⁶

¹⁵ The EQF considers that a learning outcome is “a statement of what a learner knows, understands and is able to do on completion of a learning process.”

¹⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/ploteus/content/descriptors-page> (Consulted January 2020)

EQF Level	Knowledge	Skills	Competence
	In the context of EQF, knowledge is described as theoretical and/or factual.	In the context of EQF, skills are described as cognitive (involving the use of logical, intuitive and creative thinking), and practical (involving manual dexterity and the use of methods, materials, tools and instruments)	In the context of EQF, competence is described in terms of responsibility and autonomy.
Level 1	Basic general knowledge	Basic skills required to carry out simple tasks	Work or study under direct supervision in a structured context
Level 2	Basic factual knowledge of a field of work or study	Basic cognitive and practical skills required to use relevant information in order to carry out tasks and to solve routine problems using simple rules and tools	Work or study under supervision with some autonomy
Level 3	Knowledge of facts, principles, processes and general concepts, in a field of work or study	A range of cognitive and practical skills required to accomplish tasks and solve problems by selecting and applying basic methods, tools, materials and information	Take responsibility for completion of tasks in work or study; adapt own behaviour to circumstances in solving problems
Level 4	Factual and theoretical knowledge in broad contexts within a field of work or study	A range of cognitive and practical skills required to generate solutions to specific problems in a field of work or study	Exercise self-management within the guidelines of work or study contexts that are usually predictable, but are subject to change; supervise the routine work of others, taking some responsibility for the evaluation and improvement of work or study activities
Level 5 ^[1]	Comprehensive, specialised, factual and theoretical knowledge within a field of work or study and an awareness of the boundaries of that knowledge	A comprehensive range of cognitive and practical skills required to develop creative solutions to abstract problems	Exercise management and supervision in contexts of work or study activities where there is unpredictable change; review and develop performance of self and others
Level 6 ^[2]	Advanced knowledge of a field of work or study, involving a critical understanding of theories and principles	Advanced skills, demonstrating mastery and innovation, required to solve complex and unpredictable problems in a specialised field of work or study	Manage complex technical or professional activities or projects, taking responsibility for decision-making in unpredictable work or study contexts; take responsibility for managing professional development of individuals and groups
Level 7 ^[3]	Highly specialised knowledge, some of which is at the forefront of knowledge in a field of work or study, as the basis for original thinking and/or research Critical awareness of knowledge issues in a field and at the interface between different fields	Specialised problem-solving skills required in research and/or innovation in order to develop new knowledge and procedures and to integrate knowledge from different fields	Manage and transform work or study contexts that are complex, unpredictable and require new strategic approaches; take responsibility for contributing to professional knowledge and practice and/or for reviewing the strategic performance of teams
Level 8 ^[4]	Knowledge at the most advanced frontier of a field of work or study and at the interface between fields	The most advanced and specialised skills and techniques, including synthesis and evaluation, required to solve critical problems in research and/or innovation and to extend and redefine existing knowledge or professional practice	Demonstrate substantial authority, innovation, autonomy, scholarly and professional integrity and sustained commitment to the development of new ideas or processes at the forefront of work or study contexts including research

Table 1: EQF Levels and Learning Outcomes

However, the adoption process of the EQF has proved difficult: differences have appeared when comparing general education certificates in different national systems with the EQF levels. For example, for a similar school certificate, some countries assign a level 2 or 3 (for secondary education) and others a level 4 or 5 (for higher education). This same problem has occurred with vocational education.

2.4 European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations

The European Skills, Competence, Qualifications and Occupations (ESCO) framework is a multilingual classification system that aims to bridge the communications gap between industry and those offering training through a common reference terminology. The ESCO initiative was launched in 2010 by the EU and the first version of the ESCO framework was published in July 2017.

The ESCO benefits those in the labor market and in the education and training sector in a variety of ways:

- By providing a better matching of people to jobs by employment services or electronic tools:
 - Helping employers define the set of skills, competences and qualifications for a vacant job.
 - Helping job seekers build professional profiles in a terminology that suits job vacancies
 - Enable mobility through Europe
- By supporting education and training systems in the move to learning outcomes that better meet labor market needs:
 - Supporting the provision of information to education and training institutions that can help them in the development of new curricula.
 - Helping to provide more transparent information to students on learning outcomes and the relevance of qualifications to the labor market before they commence education or training.
- By supporting evidence-based policy making:
 - Enhancing the “collection, comparison and dissemination of data in skills intelligence and statistics tools, among others, in the European Skills Panorama.”¹⁷

The ESCO is built upon three pillars: Occupations, Skills/Competences and Qualifications.

Regarding qualifications, the ESCO is based on the EQF framework and the national databases that most Member States developed or are developing, in which they assign an EQF level to each qualification and describe the expected outcome.

¹⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/esco/portal/document/mt/89a2ca9a-bc79-4b95-a33b-cf36ae1ac6db>
(Consulted January 2020)

The most relevant ESCO guiding principles are:

- Useful, ESCO aims to become the de facto standard of the identification of occupations, skills competence and qualifications.
- Accepted, ESCO aims to be voluntarily adopted by stakeholders.
- Updated, ESCO will be continuously updated and adapted.
- Flexible, ESCO does not aim to standardize the scope of occupations but to provide standard terminology.
- High-quality, different stakeholders carefully ensured the quality of the ESCO.
- Transparent and open development, results were shared with interested parties and it was open to all stakeholders.
- Machine readable and compatible with existing IT systems and standards.

2.5 Highlights and common threads in these initiatives

After reviewing these political trends in Europe, we can now extract some of the key properties that a data science skills recognition program should contain in order to be in agreement with these existing efforts.

A data science skills recognition system should:

- P1 (2015-JR-SFECT, NSAE, Europass, EQF, ESCO) be transparent, accessible and allow the easy comparison of students' skills throughout the EU
- P2 (2015-JR-SFECT, ESCO) include an assurance of quality
- P3 (2015-JR-SFECT) provide tools for their verification and validation
- P4 (2015-JR-SFECT, NSAE, Europass, EQF) include skills acquired through traditional, digital, online, and open learning, as well as the validation of informal and non-formal learning
- P5 (2015-JR-SFECT, EQF, ESCO) be compatible with the EQF
- P6 (NSAE) influence the relevance of the skills being acquired
- P7 (NSAE, Europass, ESCO) allow the digital analysis of both the demand for and the availability of skills.
- P8 (Europass) allow their use online: in platforms like the Europass, social media and on mobile devices
- P9 (EQF, ESCO) focus on learning outcomes and not on traditional measures such as hours of study

With these goals in mind, we will now look at the most common and popular methods of recognizing skills.

3 A Survey of Recognitions

3.1 Accreditations

"Accreditation [is] the formal recognition by an independent body, generally known as an accreditation body, that a certification body operates according to international standards."¹⁸

In the context of higher education in Europe, accreditation is the process by which an educational program acquires the right to grant degrees. In Europe, most accreditation agencies are endorsed by national governments and accredit all of that country's degrees. Sometimes these agencies recognize European or international accreditations and simplify the national accreditation process for programs already accredited at the European or International Level.

Requirements for accreditation vary depending on the accreditation agency. Some examples of accreditation agencies include: the Agencia Nacional de Evaluación de la Calidad y Acreditación in Spain, the UK Accreditation Service in United Kingdom, the Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology or the World Association of Conformity Assessment Accreditation Bodies.

3.2 University/Academic degrees

Of the collection of recognitions we will review, this is most certainly the one with the longest history. For example, the notion of a doctorate was established in medieval Europe and was considered to be a license to teach at the university level.¹⁹ Nowadays, the European system of university degrees (bachelor degree, master degree, and the doctorate) are used worldwide.

Accredited College and University programs have the right to award academic degrees. It should be noted that in some parts of the world, unaccredited programs (sometimes referred to as degree mills) can legally confer degrees but these degrees are often considered to be of little worth.²⁰

A great variety of requirements exist but typically four years of university study must be completed to be awarded a bachelor degree, two additional years of study for a master degree, and a significant research contribution is required for the awarding of a doctorate.

¹⁸ <https://www.iso.org/certification.html> (Consulted January 2020)

¹⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Academic_degree (Consulted January 2020)

²⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_unaccredited_institutions_of_higher_education (Consulted January 2020)

In many private and public sector jobs, both pay scales and position prerequisites are directly related to the degrees held by a candidate. In some parts of the world, holding a degree results in a change of title (Doctor for example) and in others it results in the right to use post-nominal letters (BA for example).

Noteworthy examples in Big Data/Data Science include: M.Sc. Big Data & Business Analytics, University of Amsterdam, M.Sc. Applied Informatics, Vytautas Magnus University, M.Sc. Data Science, Sapienza Università di Roma or M.Sc. Computer Science, National University of Ireland.

3.3 Certificates

A certificate is simply a document that attests to the fact that a certain individual has “received specific education or has passed a test or series of tests.”²¹ Though in reality they are very varied in use, in the context of the computing industry certificates are most commonly used to recognize knowledge regarding a specific set of skills.

There are both academic and professional certificates with the former being awarded by higher education providers while the later are awarded by professional organizations or individual companies related to their own products.

Certificates typically require less effort to obtain than an academic degree. The examples given below have a duration of between 6 and 18 months. Many certificate programs are specifically designed for 'continuing education' students who are already employed full-time but are trying to advance their career. Many academic certificates are associated with traditional coursework and are basically equivalent to having passed with a certain grade a set of courses. Most professional certificates require passing a test, some also require a certain amount of professional experience to be eligible for certification. Many professional certificates expire after a certain period of time and require renewal by completing continuing education courses and/or exams.

Corporations often require that service providers have staff with certain certifications before they can provide specific services. Often job advertisements specifically require certain certifications. For example, many Network Engineer positions require that applicants have a Cisco Certified Network Associate (CCNA) certificate.

Relevant examples of academic certificates in Big Data/Data Science include:

- Harvard Data Science Certificate:²² Cost 11,360 USD, Duration: 1.5 years, all courses can be completed online
- University of California, Irvine Data Science Certificate Program:²³ Cost: free for UCI graduate students, Duration: 32 hours of courses/workshops

²¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Academic_certificate (Consulted January 2020)

²² <https://www.extension.harvard.edu/academics/professional-graduate-certificates/data-science-certificate> (Consulted January 2020)

²³ <http://datascience.uci.edu/data-science-certificate-program/> (Consulted January 2020)

- Georgetown University Certificate in Data Science:²⁴ Cost: 7,496.00 USD, Duration: 6 months, courses held on Friday evenings and Saturdays
- UC Berkeley Certificate Program in Data Science:²⁵ Cost 5,100 USD (+ materials + registration), Duration 150 hours of class

3.4 Labels

Labels are a distinction awarded to an existing degree program. The use of the term label appears to be almost exclusively European. Like accreditations, but unlike the other recognitions mentioned here, it is applied to the program itself and is not normally thought of as being applied to the program's participants (except through association). A label publicly recognizes that the program in question meets the requirement of the label issuer.

There is no clear consensus regarding who can confer a label, but at the moment the most noteworthy labels are conferred by programs funded by the European Commission. Each organization is free to design any requirements, which it sees fit.

Noteworthy examples are Erasmus Mundus Master of Excellence, Erasmus+, EIT Digital, Euro-ace, Euro-Inf, and The European Language Label (ELL).

3.5 Badges

Badges are a very recent arrival in the skills recognition landscape. A badge is a graphical representation of any kind of achievement, goal or milestone based on a digital file that integrates the criteria and evidences used to obtain the badge.²⁶ In an industrial setting, badges seem to be a lesser and more accessible form of recognition when compared with certificates. One of the principal motivations behind the "Badge Movement" was to provide a new mechanism for the recognition of skills which is better adapted to recent changes in learning:

- Nowadays, learning happens in many different contexts and while using various kinds of media. Instead of only recognizing credentials from students enrolled in established learning institutions, employers should have a mechanism for recognizing skills (and experiences) acquired by anyone through: professional training programs, participating in competitions, volunteer programs, MOOC's etc.
- Learning is not something which should only be 'recognized' during the 'student' phase of one's career but should rather be an ongoing process.
- Traditional skills recognitions do not capture elements which cannot be easily evaluated by test scores and short-term projects.

²⁴ <https://scs.georgetown.edu/programs/375/certificate-in-data-science/> (Consulted January 2020)

²⁵ <http://extension.berkeley.edu/public/category/courseCategoryCertificateProfile.do?method=load&certificateId=28652248>. (Consulted January 2020)

²⁶ Open digital badges. *The Electronic Journal of English as a Second Language*, 18 (1), 1-11.

- Academic diplomas are for the most part monolithic documents. Recognitions of lesser granularity and much more flexibility are needed. Also, these recognitions should contain both the criteria used to evaluate the skills and evidence of the acquisition.
- Recognitions need to be digital, and capable of being displayed online

By design, badges can be awarded by any organization. Each organization is free to design any set of requirements, which it sees fit.

Noteworthy examples are IBM Digital Badges²⁷, Digital Badges at Purdue University²⁸ or Stackoverflow's badge program²⁹.

The next section compares these recognition strategies according to the main characteristics identified from the EU political trends discussed in Section 2.

3.6 A Comparison of Recognitions

We began by reviewing current political trends in Europe regarding skills recognition and then we gave a brief overview of different popular skills recognition tools. The goal of this section is to evaluate the suitability of those recognition tools based upon those previously identified European political trends along with a short list of properties specific to data science. Lastly, based upon that evaluation we will recommend a scheme for the recognition of data science skills in Europe.

3.6.1 *Properties specific to data science*

Before proceeding to the comparison, we would like to include a few additional properties not previously mentioned in Section 2.5 and which are specific to the rapidly evolving area of data science. Additionally, skills recognition in data science should:

- P10 require renewal after a set period of time
- P11 provide a framework which can quickly adapt to changes in skill requirement
- P12 measure skills on a highly granular and an individual by individual basis

3.6.2 *The comparison*

It should be noted that many of the previously recognition tools are very flexible, thus in certain cases they could or could not satisfy a certain property depending upon the implementation of the tool. When this occurs we will mark that fact with a “✓?” in the table.

²⁷ <https://www.ibm.com/services/learning/M425350C34234U21> (Consulted January 2020)

²⁸ <https://www.purdue.edu/cie/globallearning/badges.html> (Consulted January 2020)

²⁹ <http://stackoverflow.com/help/badges/> (Consulted January 2020)

Desired Property	Accreditation	University degree	Certificate	Label	Badge
P1 - transparent, accessible and allow the easy comparison of students' skills throughout the EU			✓	✓?	✓
P2- include an assurance of quality	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓?
P3 - provide tools for their verification and validation	✓?	✓?	✓?	✓?	✓
P4 - include skills acquired through traditional, digital, online, and open learning, as well as the validation of informal and non-formal learning		✓?	✓	✓?	✓
P5 - compatible with the EQF		✓?	✓	✓	✓
P6 - influence the relevance of the skills being acquired		✓?	✓	✓	✓
P7 - allow the digital analysis of both the demand for and the availability of skills			✓?		✓
P8 - allow their use online: in platforms like the Europass, social media and on mobile devices		✓?	✓?	✓?	✓
P9 - focus on learning outcomes and not on traditional measures such as hours of study		✓?	✓	✓	✓
P10 - require renewal after a set period of time			✓		✓
P11 - provide a framework which can quickly adapt to changes in skill requirement			✓	✓?	✓
P12 - measure skills on a highly granular and an individual by individual basis			✓		✓

Table 2: Comparison of different skills recognitions

3.7 Discussion

In the previous comparison, the two tools which showed the worst results were accreditations and labels. Simply put, accreditation is a tool used to ensure that an educational program meets some minimum requirements in order for it to issue degrees. As such, it is not suited for the recognition of data science skills. Labels have more promise but again are a tool used to recognize traditional educational programs as a whole and not an individual's learning outcomes. University degrees have many strong points but fall short in that they:

- are not very transparent nor individual,
- do not traditionally recognize informal and non-formal learning,
- are not very granular,
- are not traditionally digital, and lastly
- are not well suited to recognizing quickly changing skills.

Badges and certificates both offer all of the desired properties and thus our recommendation will be a mix of both of these tools.

4 Recommendations

Regarding Data Science Skills Recognition

Given that both certificates and badges manifest the properties which we found desirable in a skills recognition tool, we propose a hybrid approach drawing from the strengths of both badges and certifications.

We begin with a summary of the needs of all stakeholders in the data science ecosystem.

Data scientists need:

- (DS-N1) Credentials, which are widely recognized
- (DS-N2) Credentials, which can be easily verified online
- (DS-N3) A simple way to digitally display their skills online and in social networks
- (DS-N4) Mechanisms to formally recognize skills acquired through informal and non-formal training

Employers who hire data scientists need:

- (EM-N1) Tools to verify the authenticity of credentials
- (EM-N2) A skills recognition framework, which facilitates the comparison of candidate skills throughout the EU
- (EM-N3) Influence in the process of designing the types of training data scientists receive
- (EM-N4) A scheme for recognizing skills in data science, which can quickly adapt to changes in the data science ecosystem

Educators who train data scientists need:

- (ED-N1) Publicity for their programs and the added value that an externally branded recognition of their training can provide
- (ED-N2) Recognitions for the partial completion of their programs to assist students who are seeking employment while studying or students who abandon their studies
- (ED-N3) Contact with employers, a mechanism to clarify the changing needs of industry and clear recommendations regarding how to adapt to those needs

Accordingly, to meet these needs our recognition approach will be based on the following elements:

- The use of Open Badges. (DS-N2, DS-N3, EM-N1, EM-N4, ED-N2)
- Experts from industry and academia will contribute to both defining and maintaining the badge scheme. (DS-N1, EM-N2, EM-N3, EM-N4, ED-N1, ED-N3)

- An initial proposal regarding both the types and the requirements of the badges will be based upon the work of the EDISON and EDSA projects. These projects have focused a great deal of time and effort in establishing a consensus regarding frameworks for data science education in both industry and academia.
 - Badges will only be issued by trusted third parties. By carefully vetting badge issuers and their practices the reputation of the credentials will increase. (DS-N1, ED-N1)
 - Supposing that the badges become popular, their requirements will influence the training of data scientists, give prestige to those who issue the badges and give publicity to their branding. (EM-N3, ED-N1)
 - Include the recognition of skills acquired through informal and non-formal training. (DS-N4)

Table 3 shows that our proposal covers all of the previously identified needs.

	DS-N1	DS-N2	DS-N3	DS-N4	EM-N1	EM-N2	EM-N3	EM-N4	ED-N1	ED-N2	ED-N3
Open Badges	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪
Industry/Academic Involvement	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪
Trusted Third Parties	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪
Impact on Training and Prestige	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪
Informal/Non-formal Training	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪	▪

Table 3: Needs vs. Proposal

Though what we are recommending is really a hybrid approach inspired by aspects of certificates and badges, given the novelty and interest by large corporations such as IBM and Microsoft in the use badges, we believe that the term “badge” should be used for the data science skills recognition system.

The only disadvantage to the use of the term “badge” that we see is their current strong association with informal and non-formal learning. But in light of the growing interest, both in academia and in industry, to use badges we believe that in the medium-term that association will decrease.

4.1 The Logistics of the BDV Data Science Badge Program

In this section we will briefly describe the logistics of the BDV Data Science Badge program.

Preliminaries:

- A collection of experts, including representatives from industry and academia, establish both the types and the requirements of the badges included in the program. They also define the process for applying to issue badges.
- This group of experts also approves the members of a group of reviewers whose mission is to evaluate applications received to issue badges.

Applying to issue badges:

- Interested institutions/educators can apply to issue a badge. This application includes submitting evidence that shows that they provide their students with the skills required by the badge.
- Reviewers are assigned applications to assess and decide whether the applicant program meets the established standards to issue badges. Applications can be rejected, accepted conditionally for one year or accepted for four years.

Issuing badges:

- Students in a data science program authorized to issue BDV Badges acquire and demonstrate their data science skills through their studies. Students in the program can submit an application to their program to receive a badge.
- The program reviews badge applications and if the applicant has met the requirements of the badge then it issues the student that badge. Badges are individualized and contain metadata including: the requirements to earn the badge and evidence of the student’s achievements.

Displaying and viewing badges:

- Students can display their badges online: in their CV, in social networks, etc.
- Interested employers can: verify that a badge is valid and use its metadata to access relevant information regarding the earners of a badge.

Revision

- The group of experts will periodically meet to review the program. Based upon progress reports, they can propose changes and improvements in the program.

A graphical representation of the process for applying to issue and issuing badges is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1. BDV Badges - Application and Issuing Process

5 BDV Data Science Badges Types and Requirements

In order to define both the types and requirements of the BDV Data Science Badge program we focused on EDISON's Data Science Competence Framework (CF-DS) and Data Science Model Curriculum (MC-DS). We selected these documents as the basis of our proposal as they directly relate competences with professional profiles. So from an industrial perspective, it should be easy to understand the value of the badges through their relationships to the corresponding competences. Furthermore, the professional profiles and their required competency levels as given by EDISON can be used as an example of how the badges can be used in each organization. These examples can then be adapted to the structure and needs of an individual organization to provide a mapping between the badges and its hiring needs.

We initially proposed the creation of one group of badges for each competence group, with each group of badges having three levels of proficiency (basic, intermediate and expert). To make the proposal more accessible to a wider audience, we chose to use the term "required skills" in place of "learning outcomes."

Thus, the following is the initial collection of BDV Data Science Badges:

- Data Science Analytics Badge
- Data Engineering Badge
- Data Science Management Badge
- Business Process Management Badge
- Data Science Research Method and Project Management Badge

We also considered the possibility of creating one badge for each of the competences in each competence group. But this would have resulted in an excessively large number of badges that we thought would be unmanageable.

Though the BDV Badges are based upon the work produced by the EDISON project, it should be noted that they can also be related to EDSA's curriculum. Each badge has several required skills (or in EDISON's terminology "learning outcomes"), which relate to one or several of EDSA's topics. In this sense, the description given by EDSA for each topic constitutes one possible learning resources source. In fact, EDSA based their four learning pathways (Data Analytics, Data Science Engineering, Data Management, and Business Process Management) upon four of the five competence groups in EDISON's framework.³⁰

³⁰ <http://courses.edsa-project.eu/course/view.php?id=70> (Consulted January 2020)

5.1 Refining and Evaluating this Initial Proposal

With the aim of verifying the comprehensibility and utility of this proposal, we conducted an evaluation process which involved both industry and academia. In order to get detailed feedback and make this assessment process effective, in this initial stage we focused only on the first badge, the Data Science Analytics Badge.

Twelve companies were contacted to participate in different stages of the assessment. The aim was to obtain information about the relevance of the different required skills to their hiring practices and to ensure that the descriptions of the required skills were easy to understand.

Additionally, fifteen universities were also contacted to participate in several rounds of the evaluation. The aim was to get feedback about the review process (specifically the kinds of material to be requested of badges applicants), and about the requirements of the badge.

Finally, the members of the BDVA Skills and Education Task Force were also requested to provide their opinions on the initial version of the badges as well as on the comments gathered from industry and academy throughout the entire process.

As result of the assessment process several changes were proposed in the initial version of the requirements of the Data Science Analytics Badge. One of the most relevant ones is the replacement of the tree levels of proficiency (basic, intermediate and expert) with three different sets of required skills with two levels (academic and professional) having the same required skills. The academic level requires knowledge and training which can be acquired in an academic context, while the professional level requires real professional practice.

Furthermore, based upon comments received the descriptions of some of the requirements were modified. Some of these changes were, for example, to highlight the role of descriptive models and to separate requirements related to data preparation, data visualization and data analytics tasks. The resulting requirements for the BDV Data Science Analytics Badge are shown in Table 4 and the images of both the academic and professional badges are shown in Figure 2.

Data Science Analytics Badge v1-0
Required skills
DSA.1. Identify existing requirements to choose and execute the most appropriate data discovery techniques to solve a problem depending on the nature of the data and the goals to be achieved.
DSA.2. Select the most appropriate techniques to understand and prepare data prior to modelling to deliver insights.
DSA.3. Assess, adapt, and combine data sources to improve analytics.
DSA.4. Use the most appropriate metrics to evaluate and validate results, proposing new metrics for new applications if required.

DSA.5. Design and evaluate analysis tools to discover new relations in order to improve decision-making.

DSA.6. Use visualisation techniques to improve the presentation of the results of a data science project in any of its phases.

Table 4. BDV Data Science Analytics Badge Skills

Figure 2. Data Science Analytics Badges with academic and professional levels (v1.0)

A pilot of the entire application process to issue the Academic Level of the Data Science Analytics Badge was conducted. The goal of the pilot was to check the workflow to be followed by universities applying to issue the badge and reviewers of the applications to issue badges. Three applications were received and reviewed as part of the pilot. No major problems in the process were found and the pilot was considered to be a success. Two of the applications received as part of the pilot were accepted:

- Master in Big Data Analytics, Universitat Politècnica de València, València, Spain

Máster **Big Data** Analytics

UNIVERSITAT
POLITÈCNICA
DE VALÈNCIA

- Data and Web Science MSC Program, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece

6 Conclusions

After a survey of current trends in education in the EU was conducted, a collection of desirable properties for a data science skills recognition system was established. Those properties were compared to the benefits of existing tools for recognizing skills and a hybrid between certifications and badges was selected as the appropriate tool for recognizing skills in data science. Lastly, based upon the needs of stakeholders in the data science ecosystem, the details of a recognition system for data science skills were defined and the system was successfully piloted. At the moment of writing, the first open call for application to issue the Academic Level of the BDV Data Science Analytics Badge is open and can be found online at: <https://www.big-data-value.eu/skills/skills-recognition-program/call-for-academic-level-data-science-analytics-badge-issuers/>.